

Standard Potential of Cd_xHg_y/Cd²⁺ Electrode

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THE difference in the values of $E^0_{Cd_xHg_y/Cd^{2+}}$ from Harned and Fitzgerald's cells¹ of the type (C₁),

and from Bates' cells² of the type (C₂),

as reported by the authors exceeds even 1 mv. at lower temperature.

In our laboratory, (i) Sahu and Prasad³ determined the dissociation constant of CdCl⁺ and (ii) Sinha and Prasad⁴ determined the dissociation constant of CdBr⁺.

The e.m.f. of both the cells (C₁) and (C₂) is given by,

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln m_{Cd} m_x^2 \gamma_{Cd} \gamma_x^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

Here Cd stands for Cd²⁺ and X stands for Cl⁻ or Br⁻ and γ 's represent the activity coefficients of the species indicated by the subscripts. Applying equation (2),

$$\log \gamma_i = \frac{AZi^2 \sqrt{\mu'}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu'}} + Bi\mu' \quad \dots (2)$$

in equation (1), we get,

$$E + \frac{2 \cdot 30259 RT}{2F} (\log m_{Cd} m_x^2 - \frac{6A \sqrt{\mu'}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu'}}) = E^0 - \frac{2 \cdot 30259 RT}{2F} B\mu' \quad \dots (3)$$

The first stage of dissociation of both cadmium chloride³ and cadmium bromide⁴ has been found to be complete upto 0.01M. Further at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° equations of the type,

$$\log K_{A(c)} = \log K_c + \frac{4A \sqrt{\mu'}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu'}} - b\mu$$

have been given^{3,4} for the second stage. Here

$$K_{A(c)} = \frac{[Cd^{2+}][X^-]}{[CdX^+]}$$

and K_C (thermodynamic dissociation constant), A' and μ are on the molarity scale. Now, $c = \rho m$,

(where ρ = density of water) in very dilute solutions. Hence the above equations can be changed to the type

$$\log K_A = \log K + \frac{4A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - b\mu' \quad \dots (4)$$

In equation (4), K_A , K , A and μ' are on the molality scale. The value of b may be taken to be the same on the molality and molarity scales. The values of $\log K$ and b on the molality scale are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Temp. (°C)	For CdCl ⁺		For CdBr ⁺	
	log K	b in eqn. (4)	log K	b in eqn. (4)
5	2.0650	1.84	3.8900	5.893
15	2.0400	1.68	3.9100	7.193
25	2.0303	1.78	3.9433	5.448
35	2.0013	2.16	3.8806	8.857

If α be the degree of dissociation of CdX⁺, then,

$$m_{Cd} = \alpha m \quad \dots (5)$$

$$m_X = (1 + \alpha)m \quad \dots (6)$$

$$m_{CdX^+} = (1 - \alpha)m \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\mu' = (1 + 2\alpha)m \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$K_A = \frac{m_{Cd} m_X^2}{m_{CdX^+}} = \frac{\alpha(1 + \alpha)m}{(1 - \alpha)} \quad \dots (9)$$

For any molality of cadmium chloride at any temperature, an arbitrary value is assigned to μ' and the value of K_A is calculated from equation (4) which yields a value for α from equation (9) and a new value of μ' by equation (8). The process is repeated till α becomes constant upto the 4th place of decimal. At this stage, the correct values of m_{Cd} , m_X and μ' are calculated from equations (5), (6) and (8) respectively. This is done in case of all the solutions ($m < 0.01$) studied by Harned and Fitzgerald¹.

Now, all the terms of L.H.S. of equation (3) and μ' are known. The plot of L.H.S. of equation (3) against μ' for each temperature gives a straight line. E^0_{cell} is obtained from the intercept of the straight line at $\mu' = 0$. Now, $E^0_{Cd_xHg_y/Cd^{2+}}$ at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° are obtained by combining E^0_{cell} of cells (C₁) and (C₂) thus obtained with the appropriate values of $E^0_{Ag/AgCl, Cl^-}$ or $E^0_{Ag/AgBr, Br^-}$ as reported in the literature. For this purpose, the values of $E^0_{Ag/AgCl}$, C_1 as reported by Harned and Ehlers⁵ and the mean values of $E^0_{Ag/AgBr, Br^-}$ as found by various workers and reported in the paper of Sinha and Prasad⁶ have been used.

The recalculated (R) and the originally reported values (O.R.V.) of E^0 by (i) Harned and Fitzgerald¹ and Bates² are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—(GENEVA CONVENTION)

Temp. (°C)	E^0_{cell} (O.R.V.)	E^0_{cell} (R)	E^0 of Cd_xHg_y/Cd^{2+} in abs. m _v .	
			Coll (C ₁)	
			(O.R.V.)	(R)
5	580.39	580.20	346.5	346.3
15	577.55	577.40	349.1	348.9
25	573.90	573.90	351.5	351.5
35	569.55	569.53	353.9	353.9
Cell (C ₂)				
5	425.0	426.3	345.1	346.6
15	424.3	424.9	348.3	349.2
25	422.7	423.0	351.4	351.7
35	420.1	420.3	354.1	354.3

The recalculated values of E^0 of Cd_xHg_y/Cd^{2+} electrode from cells (C₁) and (C₂) comes within 0.4 mv. The mean of the recalculated values in volt may be represented by the equation, $-E^0_t = 0.3516 + 2.51 \times 10^{-4}(t-25) - 2.0 \times 10^{-7}(t-25)^2 \dots$ (10)

It may be mentioned that the difference in the values of E^0 reported by (i) Harned and Fitzgerald¹ and (ii) Bates² was due to wrong value of dissociation constant of $CdBr^+$ used by Bates².

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Preparation and Properties of some Mesoionic 1,4-Diphenyl-5-Aryltriazole-2-Thiones

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INFORMATION on the derivatives of mesoionic s-triazoles(I)^{1,2} are rather limited, and in this context our efforts to synthesise I from mesoionic thiadiazole (II) were not uniformly successful³.

However, the desired compounds (I) were ultimately obtained in good yield only through a minor modification of a reported procedure² involving treatment of appropriate 1,4-diaryltriosemicarbazide with an aryl chloride. Thus, a series of hitherto unreported compounds (I) were synthesized and their properties are noted in table 1.

All the compounds (I) showed the characteristic λ_{max} in the long wavelength region and the assigned structure was also consistent with the presence of C-S band⁴ around 1340 cm^{-1} . However, data on λ_{max} suggest that an electron withdrawing substituent at C-5 conjugates more effectively with the mesoionic ring than the same substituent at N-1 position. It is interesting to recall that an aryl substituent at C-4 in sydnone exhibit a similar trend when compared with the same substituent at C-5^{5,6}.

Experimental

M.ps are uncorrected (open capillary). Spectral data were obtained with Hilger Recording Spectrophotometer.

Preparation of mesoionic 1,4-diphenyl-5-aryltriazole-2-thiones (I):

1,4-Diphenylthiosemicarbazide (0.5 g) was added to a solution of an aryl chloride (prepared from 0.5 g of acid) in dry benzene (5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr on a steam bath. The clear solution usually deposited yellow material during the course of reflux. The mixture was cooled, the precipitated solid was collected and washed with dry benzene. In the absence of any solid, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the operation was repeated twice with addition of fresh benzene.

The crude product, at any event, was treated with a solution (10 ml) of sodium ethoxide (from ca 250 mg of Na) at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$). The mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature and then cooled in an ice-bath. The precipitated solid was collected, washed with ethanol and then dried. Crystallisation from ethanol (charcoal) afforded the desired compounds as shown in table 1.

1-p-Bromophenyl-4,5-diphenyl derivative (no. 9, table 1) was synthesized by using the appropriate thiosemicarbazide and benzoyl chloride. Properties of this compound were analogous to other members of the series, although it was not possible to synthesize it from II as reported earlier.³